

Yield loss per unit increase in damage by GM, YSB, and LF in five rice varieties at 3 growth stages during 2 seasons.^a Madurai, India, 1988-89.

Variety	Yield loss (%)					
	Tillering		Panicle initiation		Maturity	
	Season I	Season II	Season I	Season II	Season I	Season II
<i>Gall midge (GM)</i>						
IR20	9.0	14.0	4.0	3.0	–	–
ADT36	1.0	3.0	2.5	2.0	–	–
MDU3	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	–	–
Sona	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	–	–
IET9689	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	–	–
<i>Yellow stem borer (YSB)</i>						
IR20	3.0	8.0	2.0	7.0	1.0	13.0
ADT36	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	2.0
MDU3	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0
Sona	1.0	2.0	2.0	4.0	1.0	1.0
IET9689	8.0	1.0	12.0	1.0	4.0	2.0
<i>Leafhopper (LF)</i>						
IR20	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	10.0	10.0
ADT36	5.0	14.0	3.0	13.0	7.0	10.0
MDU3	4.0	6.0	3.5	3.0	4.0	2.0
Sona	2.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	0.5	1.5
IET9689	5.0	0.5	1.5	0.5	3.0	1.0

^aSeason I = Jun-Sep 1988, season II = Oct 1988-Jan 1989.

maximum loss from GM infestation in both seasons. GM-resistant MDU3 suffered the least damage from GM and YSB.

YSB caused heavy losses during the second season in all varieties except

IET9689, which suffered more during the first season. LF incidence accounted for heavy loss in ADT36 and MDU3 during early crop growth stages and in IR20 at later stages. □

Resistance to rice thrips in breeding lines derived from *Oryza officinalis*

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Fifty breeding lines derived from *O. officinalis* were exposed to natural infestation by thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) during August 1990 at the ACRI, Killikulam.

Each breeding line was sown in 3 rows of 5 m each and susceptible TN1 and resistant Ptb 21 were sown at random. The breeding lines were not replicated in the preliminary screening test. When the susceptible TN1 showed a rating of 9, all breeding lines were rated for thrips damage using 0-9 scale. Breeding lines that showed a damage rating of 1 in the preliminary screening test were retested in a randomized block design replicated five times. Damage

rating was done as described. Of the 50 breeding lines evaluated for thrips resistance, 17 lines exhibited high levels of resistance (see table). □

Resistance to thrips in breeding lines derived from *O. officinalis*.

Breeding line	Damage rating ^a
IR54742-1-20-10-11-2	1.0 a
IR54742-4-7-9-7-1	1.0 a
IR54742-6-1-14-15-1	1.0 a
IR54742-6-1-14-15-3	1.0 a
IR54742-6-20-9-3-1	1.0 a
IR54742-6-20-9-3-2	1.0 a
IR54742-6-34-17-11-1	1.0 a
IR54742-18-17-20-15-2	1.0 a
IR54742-22-14-24-22-2	1.0 a
IR54742-22-14-24-22-3	1.0 a
IR54742-22-19-3-7-1	1.0 a
IR54742-22-19-3-7-2	1.0 a
IR54742-22-19-3-7-3	1.0 a
IR54742-33-18-20-3-5	1.0 a
IR54742-52-10-17-8-1	1.0 a
Ptb 21	1.0 a
TN1	9.0 b

^aMean of 5 replications. Scored using the Standard evaluation system for rice (0.9). Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Reaction of summer and winter rice cultivars to hispa in Assam, India

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Hispa *Dicladispa armigera* (Oliv.) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) is a serious endemic rice pest in Assam. Fifty ahu (summer) rice cultivars from the Regional Agricultural Research Station, Titabor, Assam, were grown for 1 yr in earthen pots (40 cm diam, 36 cm deep) to screen for hispa resistance.

Pots containing ten 30-d-old seedlings each were randomly spaced at 20 × 15 cm in a 10-m² area surrounded by a white, mosquito-proof nylon net (15 × 15 × 2.5 m). Each cultivar had four replications (pots). About 14,000 field-collected adults were starved for 8 h and then released inside the net at 10/plant.

Saket 4 and Culture 1 were used as susceptible checks for summer and winter rice. Percent hispa-damaged leaves were recorded on three plants randomly selected from each replication of each variety 48 h after Saket-4 suffered 100% leaf damage.

Saket 4, Ratna, recommended modern varieties in Assam, and Culture 1 suffered more than 90% leaf damage. Eleven entries were moderately resistant

Reaction of summer and winter rice cultivars to hispa under nethouse conditions. Jorhat, Assam, India.

Variety	Leaf damage ^a (%)
<i>Summer rice</i>	
As 75	12.8
As 48	14.2
Govind	14.6
Bijer 3	15.0
Bengaubisi	15.1
As 36	16.5
Gareni	16.8
As 36/20	17.1
As 93/1	18.1
As 36/14	18.5
Mala	19.6
<i>Winter rice</i>	
Boro 1	12.5
IET10896	14.2
Govind	15.4
IET10898	15.9
IET10895	16.9

^aAv of 1989 and 1990.